

Investigating TLS Dynamics over Tropical and Subtropical Region using Ground and Satellite data

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Outline of the PhD Dissertation Presentation

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Introduction

- ▶ The Earth's atmosphere is a mixture of various gases that envelops the planet and sustains the air we breathe.
- ▶ It plays a crucial role in shielding us from UV radiation, regulating temperatures, enabling weather patterns, the water cycle, and even burning up meteors.

Figure 1: Composition of the Atmosphere and its temperature layers (image credit: <https://www.map> and [WMO.gov.png](https://www.wmo.gov))

Figure 2: Atmospheric Circulation cell and tropopause seasonal variation (Murgatroyd and O'Neill, 1980).

Cont...

- ▶ The TLS is a complex region within the Earth's atmosphere that controls the vertical distribution of aerosols, WV, O₃, and other trace constituents.
- ▶ Research data from the 63-station RS network, as cited by Angel (1990), indicates that there has been an increase in tropospheric temperature trends of around 0.3 K.
- ▶ Bencherif et al. (2006) conducted a study on temperature trends in the troposphere and stratosphere, showing ranges from – 0.08 to 0.28 K and – 1.08 to – 0.44 K respectively.
- ▶ The TLS is a highly dynamic region of the atmosphere that is influenced by factors such as deep convection, atmospheric waves, and natural forcings.

Motivation

- ▶ The TLS is a complex and dynamic region of Earth's atmosphere that plays a crucial role in influencing global climate, weather patterns and air quality.
- ▶ The main factors influencing temperature trends in the tropical and subtropical region within the TLS regions are diverse, resulting from a mix of natural and human-induced factors.
- ▶ While previous studies have extensively examined KWs in the tropical region, there is a lack of research on their behavior in subtropical regions.
- ▶ Moreover previous research has mainly focused on the $5^{\circ}N$ - $5^{\circ}S$ belt of KW observations, but we have extended this narrow latitudinal belt to include tropical (0 - $15^{\circ}N$) and subtropical (22 - $35^{\circ}N$) regions.

- ▶ Our study is pioneering in connecting the tropical and subtropical TLS regions through long term ground based and satellite observations.
- ▶ A review of existing literature has shown a scarcity of publications on temperature trends, Kelvin wave analysis, and trace gas exchange in the TLS regions of Ethiopia and Egypt, which motivates the need for this study.

Objectives

▶ General objective

- ❖ The general objective of this dissertation is to study troposphere and lower stratosphere dynamics over tropical and subtropical region using ground based and satellite data

▶ Specific objectives

- 👉 To investigate Long Term TLST trend in tropical and subtropical NH using Ground Based and Satellite data.
- 👉 To identify Kelvin waves in tropical and subtropical regions using Radiosonde and AIRS Satellite Temperature data.
- 👉 To study Troposphere–Stratosphere trace gases exchange in UTLS region over tropical and subtropical regions.

Significance of the study

The study of TLS offers numerous advantages:

- It's significance extends to weather prediction, climate modeling, air quality monitoring, ozone layer protection, and aviation safety.
- TLS studies are vital for aviation as they help accurately identify the altitude of tropospheric turbulence, eddy layers, and jet streams, enhancing flight safety and efficiency.
- The findings enhance understanding of climate change impacts, including tropospheric warming, stratospheric cooling, and their implications.

Study area

Figure 3: A comparative map of tropical Addis Ababa (Ethiopia) and subtropical Cairo (Egypt).

Data and Analysis Methods

Data Sources

- ☞ Radiosonde (<https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds351.0/>)
- ☞ COSMIC
(<https://data.cosmic.ucar.edu/gnss-ro/cosmic2/nrt/>)
- ☞ AURA MLS (<https://mls.jpl.nasa.gov/>)
- ☞ Nino 3.4 index (<https://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/data/indices/ersst5.nino.mth.91-20.ascii>)
- ☞ F10.7 (<ftp://ftp.geolab.nrcan.gc.ca/data/solarflux/monthly/averages/maver.txt>)
- ☞ QBO (<https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/met/ag/strat/produkte/qbo>)
- ☞ IOD (https://ioc3.unesco.org/oopc/state_of_the_ocean/sur/ind/dmi.php)
- ☞ aerosol (<https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov>)

Analysis Methods

- Temperature trends are calculated by using multiple linear regression

$$T(z, t) = \alpha(z) + \beta(z)t + \gamma(z)ENSO(t) + \delta(z)SF(t) + \epsilon(z)QBO(t) + \zeta(z)IOD(t) + \eta(z)Aerosol(t) + r(z, t), \quad (1)$$

$\alpha(z)$ in the above equation is in the form:

$$\alpha(z) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^2 [A_i \cos(\omega_i(t - p_i))] \quad (2a)$$

where

- $T(z, t)$ is temperature as a function of height and time.
- The coefficients α , γ , δ , ϵ , ζ and η are determined in least square
- $\omega_i = \frac{2\pi i}{12}$, t is time in month's, p_i is the phase of SAO and AO, a_0 is constant, A_i is the amplitude of SAO and AO.

Cont...

Identifications of Kelvin Wave

$$T(\lambda, d) = \sum_{i=1}^2 [A_i \sin(\omega_i(\lambda - p_i))] \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda_z = \frac{2\pi}{N} \left(\frac{\lambda_x}{\tau} - \bar{U} \right) \quad (4)$$

Gravitational Potential energy

$$E_p = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{g}{N} \frac{T'}{T} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

$$N^2 = \frac{g}{T} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \Gamma_d \right) \quad (6)$$

Where

- $\omega_i = \frac{2\pi i}{\tau}$, λ is long, p_i phase, τ periodicity, $T(\lambda, d)$ temp, and A_i ampl.
- \bar{U} , N , τ , λ_x , and λ_z are velocity of mean zonal wind, buoyancy frequency, wave period, zonal, and vertical wavelength respectively.
- $\Gamma_d = \frac{g}{c_p}$ is adiabatic lapse rate, c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure of the atmosphere.

The tropopause mass flux of trace gases is calculated by

$$F_{flux} = \rho v A \quad (7)$$

$$\rho_{O_3} = 0.0058 \frac{P}{T} C_{O_3} \quad (8)$$

$$\rho_{H_2O} = 0.0022 \frac{P}{T} C_{H_2O} \quad (9)$$

$$SMR = 0.623 \left(\frac{e_{si}}{P - e_{si}} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$e_{si} = \exp\left(9.550426 - \frac{5723.265}{T} + 3.53068 \ln(T) - 0.00728332T\right) \quad (11)$$

where

- F_{flux} is the mass flux, ρ is the density of the gas, v is the wind speed, and A cross sectional area of O_3 or H_2O cross the tropopause.
- ρ_{O_3} , ρ_{H_2O} density of ozone and WV, P and T is tropopause pressure and temperature, C is concentration of O_3 or H_2O , and e_{si} is SVP

Results and Discussions 1: Study on long term TLST trend in tropical and subtropical region using RS and COSMIC satellite data

Monthly and Composite mean TLST variability in Addis Ababa

Figure 4: Vertical distribution of temperature variability in TLS region for monthly (a & b), and composite (c & d) from RS and COSMIC data in Addis Ababa station.

Monthly and Composite mean TLST variability in Cairo

Figure 5: Vertical distribution of temp variability in TLS region for monthly (a & b), and composite (c & d) from RS and COSMIC data in Cairo station.

Tropopause height and Temperature variations in tropical station Addis Ababa

Figure 6: Frequency distribution of daily (a) CPTH in *RS*, (b) CPTH in *COSMIC*, (c) CPTt in *RS* and (d) CPTt in *COSMIC* Over Addis Ababa

Tropopause height and Temperature variations in subtropical station Cairo

Figure 7: Frequency distribution of daily (a) CPTH in *RS*, (b) CPTt in *RS*, (c) CPTH in *COSMIC* and (d) CPTt in *COSMIC* Over Cairo, Egypt.

Periodic Oscillations from Tropopause height in Tropical Station Addis Ababa

Figure 8: (a & c) Time series monthly mean CPT_h and its corresponding wavelet spectrum (b & d) in Addis Ababa station from 2006 to 2020

Periodic Oscillations from Tropopause height in Subtropical station

Figure 9: (a & c) Time series monthly mean CPT height and its corresponding wavelet spectrum (b & d) in Cairo station from 2006 to 2020

Periodic Oscillations from Tropopause Temperature in Tropical Station

Figure 10: (a & c) Time series monthly mean CPTt and its corresponding wavelet spectrum (b & d) in Addis Ababa station from 2006 to 2020

Periodic Oscillations from Tropopause Temperature in Subtropical Station

Figure 11: (a & c) Time series monthly mean CPTt and its corresponding wavelet spectrum (b & d) in Cairo station from 2006 to 2020

The Periodicity of TLST variations in Tropical Station

Figure 12: Wavelet analysis of TLST RS and COSMIC data in tropical Addis Ababa Station

The Periodicity of TLST variations in Subtropical Station

Figure 13: Wavelet analysis of TLST RS and COSMIC data in subtropical Cairo Station

Vertical distribution of AO and SAO at TLS Region

Figure 14: Amplitude (a–d) and their corresponding phases (e–h)

Atmospheric forcing

Figure 15: Monthly variation of (a) SOI, (b) IOD, (c) SFI and (d) Aerosol

Figure 16: Monthly variation of (e) QBO in zonal wind from 2006 – 2020.

The TLS temperature response to natural influences

Figure 17: Monthly mean temperature variability response to (a & f) IOD, (b & g) ENSO, (c & h) SF, (d & i) QBO, (e & j) aerosol

The lag month between natural forcing and TLS Temperature

Figure 18: Monthly mean temperature variability lag to (a & f) IOD, (b & g) ENSO, (c & h) SF, (d & i) QBO, (e & j) aerosol

TLS temperature trends over tropical and subtropical regions

Figure 19: Long term trends in the TLS Temperature variability as a function of altitude over the periods of 2006 – 2020.

Results and Discussions 2: To identify Kelvin waves in the UTLS in tropical and subtropical regions using RS and AIRS satellite data

Figure 20: Temperature data (blue) at 17 km from (a–d) Addis Ababa station and (e–h) Cairo station on March, June, September, and December 10, 2019, with a red label for the sinusoidal fit using AIRS data.

Longitude – time analysis of KW in TLS over tropical and subtropical regions

Figure 21: LTD of Temp fluctuations at latitude band of $22 - 35^{\circ}$ N and $0 - 15^{\circ}$ N at 15 km in subtropical and tropical regions.

Figure 22: LTD of Temp fluctuations at latitude band of $22 - 35^{\circ}$ and $0 - 15^{\circ}$ N at 17 km in subtropical and tropical regions.

Figure 23: LTD of Temp fluctuations at latitude band of $22 - 35^{\circ}$ and $0 - 15^{\circ}$ N at 25 km in subtropical and tropical regions.

Altitude – time analysis of KW in TLS over tropical and subtropical regions

Figure 24: Altitude-time KW signatures during different seasons in the subtropical region from RS data.

Figure 25: Altitude-time KW signatures during different seasons in the subtropical region from AIRS data

Altitude - Time temperature fluctuations in tropical region from RS data

Figure 26: Altitude time KW signatures during different seasons in the tropical region from RS data.

Altitude - Time temperature fluctuations in tropical region from AIRS data

Figure 27: Altitude time KW signatures during different seasons in the tropical region from AIRS data.

Cont...

Table 1: Summary of KW characteristics in tropical and subtropical region

KW	AIRS (tropical)				RS (tropical)			
	Spr	Sum	Aut	Win	Spr	Sum	Aut	Win
WP (τ)	10	9	10	9	14	14	15	14
PS (C_x)	143	186	84	182	121	130	98	120
VW (L_z)	13	13	8	11	9	4	4	5
TW (λ_z)	15	18	7	16	11	6	5	6

KW	AIRS (subtropical)				RS (subtropical)			
	Spr	Sum	Aut	Win	Spr	Sum	Aut	Win
WP (τ)	13	8	13	10	9	8	8	6
PS (C_x)	126	109	76	168	95	107	112	131
VW (L_z)	9	11	8	10	6	8	8	10
TW (λ_z)	12	10	6	15	9	10	10	11

Effect of KW and GW fluctuations on tropopause variability

Figure 28: (a) Daily CPTth variation, (b) KW fluctuation, and (c) GW fluctuation from March 2019 to February 2020 in RS data

Table 2: Seasonal corr coefficient of TH fluctuation with KW and GW

AW	spring	Summer	Autumn	Winter
KW	0.72	0.86	0.81	0.74
GW	0.12	0.48	-0.23	0.36

Figure 29: OLR between (a) 22 - 35⁰ N and (b) 0 - 15⁰ N

Results and Discussions 3: Trace Gas Exchange in the UTLS Region over Tropical and Subtropical Region

Monthly and annually mean UTLS WV and ozone Variation

Figure 30: Contour of water vapor and ozone profiles from 2006 to 2020 over tropical Ethiopia using MLS satellite data

Figure 31: Contour of water vapor and ozone profiles from 2006 to 2020 over subtropical Egypt using MLS satellite data

Cont...

Figure 32: Contour map of altitude–latitude representation of water vapor and ozone profiles over the tropical (0 - 20° N) and subtropical (22 - 40° N) regions.

Figure 33: Seasonal variation of vertical distribution of Water vapor over the tropical region of Ethiopia ($0 - 15^{\circ}$ N)

Figure 34: Seasonal variation of vertical distribution of O_3 over the tropical region of Ethiopia ($0 - 15^{\circ} N$)

Figure 35: Seasonal variation of vertical distribution of Water vapor over the subtropical region of Egypt (22 - 35° N)

Figure 36: Seasonal variation of vertical distribution of O_3 over the subtropical region of Egypt ($22 - 35^{\circ} N$)

Saturation mixing ration in tropical and subtropical regions

Figure 37: Relation between the tropopause temperature and SMR in tropical Ethiopia and subtropical Egypt

Mass flux of O_3 and WV across the tropopause in tropical Ethiopia and Subtropical Egypt

Figure 38: Mass flux of ozone and water vapor in the tropical region of Ethiopia and the subtropical region of Egypt

Conclusions

- ☞ AO is the primary factor driving T fluctuation in the troposphere, whereas SAO, ENSO, and QBO are in the UTLS.
- ☞ There is a noticeable 3 to 4 month lag in every oscillation above the tropopause.
- ☞ The T trend for both stations show a marked increment in the LT and UTLS, while the MT shows a declining trend.
- ☞ In Ethiopia, KW periodicity ranges from 9.2 to 14.5 days with vertical wavelengths of 3.8 to 12.5 km, while in Egypt, it ranges from 6.4 to 13.3 days with vertical wavelengths of 6 to 11.2 km.
- ☞ KW shows pronounced downward propagation, especially in summer, with maximum amplitudes of 8 K in Ethiopia and 4 K in Egypt.
- ☞ The study finds strong correlations between tropopause height and KW is 0.86 and gravity waves with tropopause height is 0.48.
- ☞ The study also identifies SAO in WVMR and AO in OVMR in Ethiopia, and TAO in WVMR and AO in OMR in Egypt.
- ☞ Egypt has a higher ozone mass flux (5 kg/s) compared to Ethiopia (3.4 kg/s), while Ethiopia has a higher water vapor mass flux (68 kg/s) compared to Egypt (30 kg/s).

Recommendations

- Future research should consider other atmospheric waves, such as tidal, Rossby, and planetary waves, to better understand the causes of the TLS phenomenon.
- We analyzed temperature trends in the TLS region using just RS data from Addis and Cairo stations, Future studies should include additional stations.
- Our analysis of trace gas exchange in the TLS region only includes ozone and water vapor, Future research should include other chemical species like carbon dioxide, methane, and sulfur dioxide as well.

Conferences

- 👉 College of Science and Maritime Academy Seminar, March 05, 2023, Bahir Dar University, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia
- 👉 11th Annual Science College Conference (ASC-2023), March 24 – 25, 2023, Bahir Dar University, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia
- 👉 2nd African Graduate Students Conference (AGSC-BDU-2023) June 09 – 10, 2023 Bahir Dar University, Bahir Dar, Ethiopia
- 👉 4th International Space and Planetary Science Conference (SPSC-2024), June 05 – 06, 2024, Adiss Ababa, Ethiopia

Articles

- 👉 1st article published in Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics
- 👉 2nd article submitted in Journal of Advance Space Research
- 👉 3rd article submitted in Journal of Atmosfera

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Research paper

Study on long term troposphere lower stratosphere temperature (TLST) trend in tropical and subtropical northern hemisphere using ground based and COSMIC satellite data

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